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Review Article

A Review Article On Diabetic Neuropathy

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ABSTRACT

Neuropathy is the most common complication of diabetes. As a consequence of longstanding hyperglycemia, a downstream metabolic cascade leads to peripheral nerve injury through an increased flux of the polyol pathway, enhanced advanced glycation end-products formation, excessive release of cytokines, activation of protein kinase C and exaggerated oxidative stress, as well as other confounding factors. Although these metabolic aberrations are deemed as the main stream for the pathogenesis of diabetic microvascular complications, organ-specific histological and biochemical characteristics constitute distinct mechanistic processes of neuropathy different from retinopathy or nephropathy. Heart rate variability (HRV) is an important tool to analyze the autonomic function. It therefore has a special interest for early detection and ensuing treatment of autonomic neuropathy in diabetic patients. The aim of this work is to present a brief historical review of HRV, as well as a technical review of the most common methods to measure it. In this work is presented a system that performs three measurements of HRV. An overview of methodologies developed to quantify HRV is presented; this technical review covers the most common time and frequency domain techniques, for short and long periods of time, with comments about clinical utility of these tests.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic neuropathy is a type of nerve damage that can occur in people with diabetes. It is caused by high blood sugar, which can injure nerves throughout the body. There are four main types of diabetic neuropathy, and the symptoms depend on the type and which nerves are affected. The condition can cause pain, numbness, and problems with the digestive system, urinary tract, blood

vessels, and heart. The exact cause of diabetic neuropathy is not fully known, but it is believed to be multifactorial, involving factors such as high blood sugar, metabolic factors, and the degeneration of nerve fibers and neurons. Peripheral neuropathy is the most common and intractable complication of diabetes^{1,2}. It involves somatic sensory and motor nerves, as well as

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autonomic nerves. In fact, the prevalence of diabetic neuropathy ranges from 7% within 1 year of diagnosis to 50% for those with diabetes for >25 years. If patients with subclinical levels of neuropathic disturbances are included, the prevalence might exceed 90%⁴. The presence of cardiovascular autonomic neuropathy dramatically shortens the patients' longevity and increases the mortality^{5,6}. Loss of feeling in the lower limbs is a high risk for limb amputation, which occurs in 1–2% of diabetic patients and necessitates extreme cost.

Causes

Diabetic neuropathy is nerve damage that often occurs in people with diabetes, mainly due to long-term high blood sugar levels. Here are the main causes:

1. High Blood Sugar Levels:

When blood sugar is consistently high, it can damage nerve cells. This process, known as glycation, creates harmful compounds that interfere with normal nerve function, leading to pain, tingling, or numbness.

2. Poor Blood Circulation:

Diabetes can harm blood vessels, reducing blood flow to the nerves. This means nerves don't get enough oxygen and nutrients, which are vital for their health.

3. Inflammation:

Many people with diabetes experience chronic low-level inflammation. This ongoing inflammation can release chemicals that damage nerve tissues, worsening nerve problems.

4. Metabolic Factors:

Conditions like obesity and insulin resistance often accompany diabetes and can further increase the risk of nerve damage by making blood sugar control harder.

5. Nutritional Deficiencies:

Not getting enough essential nutrients, especially B vitamins (like B1, B6, and B12) and vitamin D,

can harm nerve function and worsen neuropathy symptoms.

6. Alcohol Use:

Drinking too much alcohol can directly damage nerves and hinder the absorption of important nutrients, particularly B vitamins. It can also cause fluctuations in blood sugar levels, complicating diabetes management.

- feeling in the legs, especially below the knee.

- **Aching:**

A constant, mild pain that is uncomfortable but not severe.

- **Weakness:**

A feeling of lacking strength, which can make you feel weak or feeble. Diabetic neuropathy is a complication of diabetes that affects the nerves and can lead to various symptoms. Here's a breakdown of the main types:

Type of diabetic neuropathy

1. Peripheral Neuropathy

This is the most common type and mainly affects the nerves in the limbs, especially the feet and hands. Symptoms can include:

- Numbness and tingling
- Burning sensations
- Sharp pains
- Loss of balance

It can be further divided into:

- **Motor Neuropathy:**

Impacts muscle control and movement.

- **Sensory Neuropathy:**

Affects the ability to feel pain, temperature, and touch.

- **Autonomic Neuropathy:**

Involves involuntary body functions, like heart rate and digestion.

- **Combination Neuropathies:**

A mix of two or more types.

2. Autonomic Neuropathy

This type affects involuntary functions of the body, such as:

- Heart rate
- Digestion
- Urinary function
- Sexual function
- Sweating

It can lead to issues like not being aware of low blood sugar, heart problems, digestive issues (like delayed stomach emptying), and difficulties with bladder control or sexual response.

3. Proximal Neuropathy

This type usually causes pain in the thighs, hips, or buttocks, often on one side. It can lead to weakness in the legs and difficulty standing up. Fortunately, it's often reversible with good blood sugar management and physical therapy.

4. Focal Neuropathy

This type appears suddenly and affects specific nerves, often in the head, torso, or legs. Symptoms might include:

- Double vision
- Facial paralysis (like Bell's palsy)
- Severe localized pain

Diagnosis :

Diagnosing diabetic neuropathy involves several key steps to evaluate nerve function:

1. Medical History:

Doctors will look at your blood sugar control over time and ask about any symptoms you might have, such as numbness, tingling, or weakness.

2. Physical Examination:

• Neurological Exam:

This involves checking your reflexes, muscle strength, and how well you can feel sensations like light touch, pain, temperature, and vibrations.

• Foot Examination:

The doctor will inspect your feet for any injuries, ulcers, or deformities and assess circulation.

3. Sensory Testing:

• Monofilament Test:

A thin filament is used to test sensation in your feet; if you can't feel it, it may indicate neuropathy.

• Vibration Perception Test:

A tuning fork is used to check if you can feel vibrations on your skin.

4. Electrophysiological Tests:

• Nerve Conduction Studies (NCS):

These tests measure how quickly electrical signals travel through your nerves; slower speeds can indicate damage.

• Electromyography (EMG):

This evaluates the electrical activity in your muscles to identify any damage to motor nerves.

5. Autonomic Testing:

This assesses how well your autonomic nervous system is functioning, which controls involuntary bodily functions like heart rate and blood pressure.

6. Imaging Studies:

In some cases, MRI or ultrasound may be used to rule out other nerve-related issues.

7. Blood Tests:

These can check for vitamin deficiencies (especially B vitamins), thyroid function, and other metabolic disorders that might contribute to neuropathy.

8. Additional Assessments:

A skin biopsy may be done to look at nerve fiber density, especially if small fiber neuropathy is suspected.

CONCLUSION :

Diabetic sensorimotor polyneuropathy affects many patients with diabetes and often leads to significant pain. As the prevalence of diabetes increases, so does the incidence of this condition. Currently, nerve conduction studies and skin biopsies are key diagnostic tools for assessing nerve dysfunction. Managing diabetes is crucial for modifying the disease, but recent research shows that controlling blood sugar alone may not be enough to prevent neuropathy, particularly in type 2 diabetes. This highlights the need for more

understanding and new treatment options beyond just glucose management. Painful diabetic neuropathy is often overlooked and inadequately treated, presenting an opportunity to enhance patient care. While there is strong evidence supporting the use of certain medications—such as antiepileptic drugs, SNRIs, and tricyclic antidepressants—as first-line treatments, more research is necessary to identify new drugs and effective combinations. Future studies should focus on standardized pain assessments, longer evaluation periods, and cost-effectiveness of treatments.

REFERENCE :

1. www.google.com
2. internet:www.diabetic.niddk.nih.gov
3. www.link.springer.diabeticneuropathy.com
4. review article: Experimental diabetic by A.A.F.Sima, K.Sugimoto [1,2][4][5,6]
5. Bansal V, Kalita J and Misra UK: Diabetic neuropathy. *Postgrad Med J* 82: 95-100, 2006.
6. Kaur S, Pandhi P and Dutta P: Painful diabetic neuropathy: An update. *Ann Neurosci* 18: 168-175, 2011.
7. Román-Pintos LM, Villegas-Rivera G, Rodríguez-Carrizalez AD, Miranda-Díaz AG and Cardona-Muñoz EG: Diabetic polyneuropathy in type 2 diabetes mellitus: Inflammation, oxidative stress, and mitochondrial function. *J Diabetes Res* 2016: 3425617, 2016.
8. Dyck PJ, Kratz KM, Karnes JL, Litchy WJ, Klein R, Pach JM, Wilson DM, O'Brien PC, Melton LJ III and Service FJ: The prevalence by staged severity of various types of diabetic neuropathy, retinopathy, and nephropathy in a population-based cohort: The rochester diabetic neuropathy study. *Neurology* 43: 817-824, 1993
9. Young MJ, Boulton AJ, MacLeod AF, Williams DR and Sonksen PH: A multicentre study of the prevalence of diabetic peripheral neuropathy in the United Kingdom hospital clinic population. *Diabetologia* 36: 150-154, 1993.

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